
ACTION AND REFLECTION IN TEACHER EDUCATION

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With the spread and development of English around the world and its increased use in Uzbekistan, research about improved methods to develop students' English level has become of great importance. This has promoted changes in both the teaching and learning process.

Teachers of English must be fluent in a foreign language and must demonstrate high foreign language communicative competence. However, not all the students of language faculties and specializations reach this level. Thus, there raises the question about a search for new approaches, methods and means of formation of foreign language communicative competence of future teachers of English at the University.

Throughout the world, teacher education is the most important issue. This graduation work focuses on recent trends and experiences in the world and Uzbekistan where external pressures have caused tension between the technician model of teacher education, in which teachers learn primarily on the job alongside colleagues, and traditional forms of teacher education based in higher education institutions. This tension superficially replicates an old dichotomy between practice and theory. The contributors to this research reflect on ideas and attempts to integrate theory and practice.

The requirements for professional communicative competence of future teachers of foreign language include such speech quality and speech behavior as the correctness, accuracy, clarity, expressiveness, richness of language; logic, argumentation, evidence of given conditions, the ability to defend own point of view in a dispute; the ability to listen to the communication partner, tact, care; the ability to build a strategy of speech behavior in different situations. As a result, a whole complex of forms and methods for developing students' communicative competence should be directed to the acquisition of speech skills which permit to effectively solve professional (in this case, teaching) tasks. The analysis of the structure of professional activity of future teachers of foreign language shows that it does not take into account the modern training requirements to the professional development, which are expressed in the English language as an important part of their communicative competence. The significance of this provision is noted in the normative documents determining the development of the education system for the nearest future, particularly in the requirements of Federal state educational standards of the third generation (FSES).

The process of thinking back on and considering experiences, in order better to understand the significance of such experiences. Reflection is thought to be an important component of learning in teacher development and is often a focus of teacher development activities.

An approach to teaching and to teacher education, which is based on the assumption that teachers can improve their understanding of teaching and the quality of their own teaching by reflecting critically on their teaching experiences.

In teacher education programs, activities which seek to develop a reflective approach to teaching aim to develop the skills of considering the teaching process thoughtfully, analytically and objectively, as a way of improving classroom practices.

Foreign language teachers develop insights into their students’ learning from observing their behavior. Reflective teachers analyze the students’ behaviors, identify potential problems, modify their teaching practices, and evaluate the results. Some ideas succeed; others fail—sometimes surprisingly. This process is called action research. Action research is classroom-based research conducted by teachers in order to reflect upon and evolve their teaching. It is a systematic, documented inquiry into one aspect of teaching and learning in a specific classroom. The purpose of teacher research is to gain understanding of teaching and learning within one’s classroom and to use that knowledge to increase teaching efficacy/student learning. Reflective teachers do this every day, only not as carefully and systematically. With training and support, you can learn how to systematize your inquiry from informal reflection and teacher story sharing to formal research.

One of the growing interests in teacher education lies in how and what teachers learn across time and in the globalized world and technologies of today’s society. Teacher research has been implemented in teacher education programs as a powerful, exploratory tool for teacher candidates to inquire about educational problems and to improve their knowledge of teaching practice.

The fundamental characteristics of action-research according to Elliott, one of its pioneers, are the following (1990):

- It analyses the human actions and social situations that students and teachers experience.
- It uses an exploratory approach
- It aims to explain what happens in the classroom in relation to specific teaching contents.
- It interprets the different classroom events from the point of view of those who take part in each situation; that is, it involves teachers and students: their beliefs, values, intentions, decisions, ...

- It uses a very direct and simple language to explain the classroom situations that are analysed far from the technical and specialised language used by conventional research.

Action research typically involves small- scale investigative projects in the teacher’s own classroom, and consists of a number of phases which often recur in cycles:

Stages in action research

There are four classic developmental phases of action research:

Phase 1: Develop a *plan of action* to

- a) improve what is already happening or
- b) identify and examine a "puzzle" or problem area in your teaching.

Phase 2: *Act* to implement the plan.

Phase 3: *Observe* the effects of action in the context in which it occurs.

Phase 4: *Reflect* on these effects.

Nevertheless, other authors establish the following eight stages:

Stage 1. The identification, evaluation and formulation of the problem.

Stage 2. Preliminary discussion and negotiations amongst interested parties – teachers, advisers, researchers, sponsors – culminating in a draft proposal.

Stage 3. Review of research literature and comparable studies.

Stage 4. Restatement of the problem, or formulation of a hypothesis; explicit discussion of the assumptions underlying the project.

Stage 5. Selection of research procedures, allocation of resources, choice of materials and methods, etc.

Stage 6. Choice of evaluation procedures - bearing in mind that evaluation will be continuous.

Stage 7. The implementation of the project itself, including data collection and analysis, monitoring and feedback.

Stage 8. The interpretation of the data; inferences to be drawn; overall project evaluation.

The study aimed at understanding the factors that may contribute to the success of in-service teacher education, by identifying training rationalities that enable professional learning and institutional changes; and the mediation devices between in-service teacher education and changes in their professional practices. The issues of the study highlight the difficulties that in-service teacher education has been experiencing in creating professional practices that are appropriate to the situation of school crisis, which presents new challenges and new social mandates to teachers' work. It is relevant to say that the training logics that are produced by the school can re-enable the processes of collective learning that define *the rules of the game* within the organization. If, according to the reality of education is transformed by the reconstruction of representations of projects, attitudes, their own identity and the values of the actors, this reconstruction must be addressed in its entire social and organizational dimension. As teacher education is focused in the school, it also focuses on the problems of its operation and can therefore facilitate the construction of devices that not only enable the confrontation, but also the production of new systems of action, that result from a common project to maximize the transformation of the institution. The dynamics of the research activities that were developed took the school as a starting point, to make new relationships between theoretical and practical discourses. These relationships also produced new knowledge and the construction of devices that facilitated instituting changes that make the training dimension of the organizational contexts and the work situations more visible.

The concept of *reflective teacher* stands out as central to the change of a school, but not integrated into an *epistemological norm* that defines a priori that the model must obey. The concept can only be adequate for a “(...) movable, unstable field worked by the actors and that is critically, constantly redefined by the operations that are tried, with success or failure,” involving them and imposing positions. If the social construction of school pre-supposes a collective learning process, the *reflective teacher* must be re-evaluated on a level of collaboration and professional and organizational interaction that provides a way to shift concrete professional thinking to individual professional formal thinking in order to design the knowledge for how to act professionally, as an individual as well as collectively. The reconstruction and formalization of professional knowledge by teachers is an *open door* for a meaningful and fertile communication between two worlds that have been separated: the world of theory and research and the world of practice.

The results of the study allowed the role of the trainer, teachers, schools and research in organizing and promoting in-service teacher education to be reconceptualized. Teachers’ continued training, focused on educational settings, on the problems they pose to the work of teachers and on the production of professional and educational knowledge, creating new devices and mediation characters that can make a difference. This difference relates to the actual effect of in-service teacher education in changing educational practices in the classroom and in school.

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